

Co-funded by the European Union

DEN-CUPID

Digital Educational Network For Cultural Projects Implementation And Direction

4nd Newsletter

Third workshop (Futuro Digitale)

Open data, social media and cultural enterprises – these are the key words of the third intensive working session for cultural experts of Den-Cupid project financed by Erasmus plus. It was held in Cori, a quaint small town near Rome (60 kms south) that is crossed by Francigena route.

Den-Cupid is the framework of a sort of transnational incubation lab on ideas and cultural projects of entrepreneurs, experts, practitioners. Universities, SMEs, coaches, public authorities have all collaborating to create momentum for culture in Lazio region (where Cori is based).

<http://den-cupid.eu>

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FuturoDigitale
DEN-CUPID
Digital Educational Network For Cultural Projects Implementation And Direction

FORMAZIONE INTERNAZIONALE PER OPERATORI CULTURALI, AMMINISTRATORI PUBBLICI, ESPERTI CULTURALI

CORI, 18 - 23 FEBBRAIO 2018

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Logos of partner organizations: A, e.trikala, FIS, VealGlobal, etc.

Presentation of the DEN CuPID project by ms. Papaconstantinou

Each day had intensive theoretical sessions with different experts and local visits in order to have a practical approach in terms of cultural management.

After the workshop, Futuro Digitale has intensively worked to communicate and implement the project activities (follows in the next paragraph).

Fourth workshop (UBBSLA)

“Exploring cultural heritage in Varna, Bulgaria – 100+ years of history and life” was the focus of the 4th and the final workshop organized in Varna during 14-17 May 2018. More than 30 participants representing project partners took part in the workshop and experienced theoretical knowledge and practical exercises. The main objective was to explore the cultural heritage of Varna as an important industrial, tourist, commercial and maritime city in the North East Bulgaria and in the Bulgarian Black Sea region.

Visit to local culture heritage places, monuments, museums was part of the training agenda where the participants could learn more about the history and transformation of Varna during the years of existence. Following this, a round walking trip in the central and oldest part of Varna was made, among which the Archaeological museum, the History of Varna Museum and the unique Museum of Glass processing near Varna were visited.

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New Synergies that came up from the workshops

The third and fourth semesters of DEN CuPID project were particularly prolific in collaborations and synergies among trainees as well as among their organizations and the partners of the DEN CuPID Partnership. We feel, therefore, particularly proud to announce that two new Erasmus+ project proposals were submitted in the last call of March 2018 and two more are on the way to be submitted in the call for Youth mobility projects on the 4th of October. In detail:

During the second workshop in Trikala and the respective presentation of projects by the trainees there were intensive discussions on ways to further collaborate, as affinities were traced between specific groups of projects transnationally. Therefore, aided by the mentors of the project, two groups prepared and submitted proposals to Erasmus+ KA2 in March 2018. The first one was initiated by Spanish trainee Laura Velasco in collaboration with Gogo Kambiotou-Liapi from the municipality of Tanagra, aided by Time Heritage, and focused on cultural heritage protection and enhancement; the second one was initiated by Greek trainee Constantinos Asikis from the municipality of Farkadona with the collaboration of Futuro Digitale, University of Patras and Time Heritage, and focused on rural regeneration through the valorization of local cultural heritage.

Regarding the submissions to the Erasmus+ Youth mobility call, the first one, focusing on accessibility to museums for people with sight problems, will be led by the Municipal Gallery of Corinth and its director, Tonia Tzanavara, whereas the other one will be led by project partner Time Heritage and will focus on young professionals' training on Cultural Heritage protection in remote areas.

Dissemination Activities

e-trikala

One more Annual Conference from the Major Cities of Europe, It Users Group, to which the Municipality of Trikala and the Developmental Company of the city of Trikala, e-Trikala S.A are members of, took place in the German city of Leipzig between 28th and 30 of May 2018.

Municipality of Trikala and e-Trikala S.A was represented in the three days Conference- by Mrs Christina Karaberi from the Department of Research and Communication of e-Trikala S.A.

During the Conference E-Trikala took the opportunity to further disseminate via a stand and presentations Den- CupID project.

Time Heritage

Aphrodite Kamara from Time Heritage, Christina Karaberi from e-trikala and Nota Pantzou from the University of Patras will enjoy the Conference of ECHOPOLIS 2018 "Nature and Culture-based strategies and solutions for cities and territories" to be held 26-28 November 2018 in Athens, Greece. Their presentation, entitled: "Effective management and enhancement of local cultural resources: the DEN-CuPID paradigm and training", has been already accepted.

Aphrodite Kamara will also present a paper in the conference of ICOMOS to be held in Athens in September 14th-15th 2018: "Safeguarding the Values of the European Cultural Heritage". As part of her already accepted paper with the title: "Working with local communities on valorization and protection of heritage: the experience of European-funded projects", she will speak among others about the DEN CUPID project.

Once again, Time Heritage will be present in EUROMED 2018, the 6th International Euro-Mediterranean Conference, a conference on Digital Heritage, to be held 29/10-3/11/2018 in Cyprus. The paper, already submitted, has the significant title "Is E-learning Really Flexible? Ideas for Building Groundbreaking Interactive Learning Environments Online" and is based on our experience of the e-learning platform of DEN-CuPID.

Futuro Digitale

As Italian team, we have put forward the importance of open data in cultural management, organising a small conference during the Italian week of Open Administration - different municipalities and competent authorities participated to share their practices and discuss about the impact that open data have in terms of public management

What is more, different local workshops (in March and April 2018) were organised to share basic training practices with tourism centres of Latina county (where Cori, the town that hosted the third international Den-Cupid training).

We are trying to raise awareness with different stakeholders because we strongly believe that European projects can give new views and perspectives to peers who share common interests. Also local newspapers have been attracted, thanks to the great work that trainees are doing. So, more people have been interested.

The DEN-cuPID Survey

In the context of DENcuPID a survey was designed. Its aim was to assess the situation regarding local cultural assets and practices, and record the needs and attitudes of those involved in cultural heritage projects, such as local authorities, NGOs, cultural societies, private institutions and local businesses. Focus was centered on the program's partner countries: Bulgaria, Greece, Italy and Spain.

The DENcuPID partners helped translate the questionnaire, evaluate the content of the survey and finally distribute it. The survey which comprised 28 questions and was organized in five sections, was set up with the online survey tool “survey monkey”. Although further research is required about the topic, survey results highlighted some interesting issues. Most of the survey participants felt that their local cultural heritage is not adequately managed and promoted. They also stressed the difficulties one faces when involved in cultural heritage projects, with lack of funding and proper management being among the major obstacles. What is more striking except for Spanish participants, those involved in cultural projects have little or no prior knowledge of heritage management. Nonetheless, acknowledging the importance of efficient heritage management, they are eager to get training on the topic.

Finally, the results helped decide upon methodologies used for workshops and platforms and design and develop high quality and innovative tools and training hands on and online courses for training and coaching municipalities' employees and local actors involved or interested in cultural management projects and ventures.

Future Dissemination Activities

In August, the survey results will be presented to the participants of the Parrhasian Heritage Park Field School held in the Peloponnese. The Greek participants of the Field School are going to be encouraged to sign up on DENcuPID's educational platform and do the course. This Fall, apart from the ECHOPOLIS conference, members of the University of Patras team will also present the DENcuPID program in an one day conference organised by Pelion Oros in October at Volos with the them “Small Museums in times of Economic Crisis”.

TANAGRA EXPRESS

Synergies

Thanks to the DEN CUPID workshops, a representative of the Municipality of Tanagra, and one of the NGO DIADRASIS met and set up a joint project. The NGO DIADRASIS designed, a set of educational activities “The Tanagra Express” namely an imaginary journey with the history-train, full of educational games on the local history. The activities were offered to 5th and 6th graders of primary school.

The aim of this educational program, designed especially for the Municipality of Tanagra, was to familiarize local children with the archaeological sites, the monuments and the history of their region. The training programme took place on May 26 and 27 and on June 2 and 3 2018. It was divided into 5 actions, one in each municipal unit of the Municipality. The activity ended with a big open event in Schimatari, where all the children who took part in the these educational activities have presented to their community what they have learnt.

Educational Platform (e-trikala)

One of the project's intellectual outputs is the creation of an Educational platform, that allows all stakeholders, trainees and people that are interested in learning about cultural management to study on line the educational material prepared by the project's partners and follow tests that will evaluate their level of understanding. Furthermore, the platform serves as a networking space, where participants can communicate and share ideas among themselves or with experts and even attend via live streaming any future workshops. This platform is now finalized and can be accessed via the following link.

<http://edu.den-cupid.eu/>

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